

Performance: Modal Kombat Plays PONG

David Hindman and Evan Drummond

Modal Kombat Plays Pong is the latest edition from the NYC Modal Kombat squad, providers of guitar-controlled video game entertainment since 2004. Building on technology that allows Real guitars to control characters in video games, this latest work pits two guitarists against each other as their fretwork maps seamlessly to the positions of paddle-avatars in the classic video game PONG. The result is a performance that fuses a modern-day interpretation of “dueling banjos” with the entertaining spectacle of the public video game competition. www.modalkombat.com